

Basicity of ammonia versus phosphine : A new approach

Bidyut Saha^{*a} and Rumpa Saha^{a,b}

^aDepartment of Chemistry, The University of Burdwan, Golapbag, Burdwan-713 104, West Bengal, India

E-mail : b_saha31@rediffmail.com

^bK.G. Engineering Institute, Bishnupur, Bankura-722 122, West Bengal, India

Ammonia is more basic than phosphine. In most of the text book it is explained on the basis of high electron density on nitrogen atom due to its smaller size compared to phosphorus atom¹. We are giving rather a better explanation. In fact, NH₃ is sp₃ hybridized whereas in PH₃ there is overlap among pure *p* orbitals of phosphorus and hydrogen 1*s* orbitals². In NH₃ the participating orbitals are more or less same energy (2*s* and 2*p*). But in PH₃ the participating orbitals (3*s* and 3*p*) are not of same energy. In NH₃ the lone pair electrons resides on sp₃ hybrid orbital whereas in PH₃ the lone pair electrons resides on 3*s* atomic orbital. This is reflected from *p*- and *s*-character calculation³.

In NH₃ *p*-character of hybrid orbital overlapped with hydrogen 1*s* orbital :

$$\cos(\widehat{H\hat{N}H}) = (p - 1)/p$$

Saha & Saha

$$\cos 106^\circ 48' = (p - 1)/p$$

$$p = 0.78$$

p -character of the hybrid orbital containing lone pair = $3 - 3 \times 0.78 = 0.65$

$$s\text{-character} = 0.35$$

In PH_3 p -character of hybrid orbital overlapped with hydrogen $1s$ orbital :

$$\cos(\text{H}\hat{\text{P}}\text{H}) = (p - 1)/p$$

$$\cos 94^\circ = (p - 1)/p$$

$$p = 0.93$$

p -character of the hybrid orbital containing lone pair = $3 - 3 \times 0.93 = 0.21$

$$s\text{-character} = 0.79$$

As PH_3 lone pair electrons reside on orbital of greater s -character, it will not donate its electrons easily as nitrogen will.

References

1. R. L. Dutta, "Inorganic Chemistry. Part II : Chemical elements and their compounds", 6th ed., The New Book Stall, Kolkata, India, pp. 139.
2. A. K. Das, "Fundamental Concepts of Inorganic Chemistry. Part II", 1st ed., CBS Publishers and Distributors, New Delhi, pp. 466.
3. A. K. Das, "Fundamental Concepts of Inorganic Chemistry. Part II", 1st ed., CBS Publishers and Distributors, New Delhi, pp. 469.